

Thermoresponsive oil-continuous bigels from interpenetrating colloidal particle networks

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ABSTRACT: Gels comprising binary mixtures of polymers or particles are promising routes to soft materials with vastly improved properties. Recent work has shown the assembly of bigels or double network gels in polar environments; yet the realization of similar systems in apolar solvents has remained elusive. We present a new class of thermo-responsive oil-continuous bigels, formed by sequential assembly of sphere-like silica and platelet-like lipid colloidal particles with short-range attractions, into two discrete percolated gel networks as visualized by confocal microscopy. The ease-of-assembly make bigels suitable for fabrication of 3D-printed soft constructs. Depending on mixture composition, bigels can vastly stiffen, exceeding the elasticity predicted by

the sum of the monogels' elastic moduli by up to an order of magnitude, and toughen, bearing larger strains/stresses prior to induce yielding or material fluidization. The unusual mechanics suggest shear-activated cooperative effects, seemingly arising from mutual steric hindrance and restricted particle mobility due to interpenetration of gel networks.

INTRODUCTION

Assembly of attractive colloids involves a self-equilibration process characterized by spinodal decomposition, and emergence of mechanical metastability attained by isotropic percolation of isostatic particles.¹ These processes result in the formation of an amorphous stress-bearing space-spanning network: the colloidal gel. Colloidal gels are characterized by highly interesting internal dynamics and related mechanics, which have been extensively studied in material science and exploited in ceramic processing, foods, soft matter, direct-ink writing, etc. Over the last decades, several routes have been proposed to create colloidal gels using single short-range attractive colloidal particles, dipolar colloids, patchy colloids, among others.^{2,3} Recent efforts of paramount importance involve the assembly of binary particles, e.g. DNA-coated colloids, into double gels or 'bigels' which comprised two discrete space-filling networks and formed through demixing of colloidal species akin to single-type gels.^{2,4-6} Bigels pose opportunities for obtaining new functional materials since their 'composite' nature allows for additional degrees of freedom, namely by varying the type and interaction potential of the particles during the self-assembly process. Recent theoretical predictions and computer simulations in binary sphere-sphere or rod-sphere mixtures endowed with short-range attractive interactions indicate that bigels can be either softer or stiffer and sustain larger deformations under shear loading.^{2,15} Similar uncharacteristic

mechanics such as toughening, experimentally demonstrated in double-network polymeric hydrogels, hint that similar mechanical properties could manifest on particle bigels.⁷⁻¹⁴ Moreover, the assembly of double gels by lipophilic polymers or colloidal particles has been scarcely investigated or even not at all, which hinders their potential in oil-based materials applications, e.g. coating and 3D printing.

In this paper, we demonstrate the first realization of bigel networks arising from binary colloidal particles dispersed in a nonpolar solvent, oil. These structures are formed through spontaneous self-assembly of two type of ‘primary’ asymmetric building blocks: spherical-like fumed silica ($R_g \approx 13 \pm 10$ nm) and platelet-like tripalmitin crystals ($R_g \approx 440 \pm 30$ nm), which display attractive van der Waals interactions. The gel networks span length-scales from approximately 10 nm to 100 μm .^{16,17} We used these pair of particles due to: i) thermoresponsiveness, i.e. melting of tripalmitin above the solid-liquid phase transition temperature, $T_m \approx 52$ °C at $\phi \approx 0.10$, allowing sequential gelation, ii) selective short-range interactions,¹⁶⁻¹⁸ which is a requirement for the formation of individual double colloidal gel networks and iii) ubiquity in technological applications in oil-based colloidal suspensions and particle-reinforced materials. Motivated by the potential technological applications of bigels, we first demonstrate the suitability of bigels for fabrication of 3D-printed soft constructs which display good resolution and structural consistency. We then employ shear rheology and confocal microscopy to probe the dynamics and microstructure of bigels and monogels at similar volume fractions. Our results show that bigels can display larger modulus, bear larger deformations/stresses than monogels at similar volume fraction. Paradoxically, bigels appear microstructurally more tenuous than lipid monogels as clustering and particle mobility is arguably limited by the silica gel network. These uncharacteristic stiffening, which cannot be

accounted by the dual contribution of the elastic constants of monogels, and toughening hint cooperative effects between the non-mutually attractive gel networks that could be elicited during shear because of steric hindrance and restricted particle aggregate mobility.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials: Soybean oil (S7381) and tripalmitin (T8127) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. Hydrophilic fumed silica Aerosil® 300 was obtained from Evonik. The densities of the materials were 0.92 g/cm^3 at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (soybean oil), 0.8901 g/cm^3 at $47 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (supercooled tripalmitin) and 2.2 g/cm^3 (fumed silica).¹⁹

Preparation of gels: For the first gel network, we used fumed silica, a type of colloidal silicon dioxide produced by a pyrolysis process during which small primary particles ($R_g \approx 13 \pm 10 \text{ nm}$) form aggregates due to diffusion-limited growth that then agglomerate into hyper-branched mass fractal structures due to reaction-limited aggregation. For the second network, we employed tripalmitin ($R_g \approx 440 \pm 30 \text{ nm}$) which below their solid-liquid phase transition temperature T_m (~ 48 - $58 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ depending on volume fraction) form primary crystal nanoplatelets that aggregate into fractal clusters making up a network. Upon heating above the solid-liquid phase transition T_m , triglyceride crystal networks melt and dissolve in the continuous oil phase, losing their structural integrity. Whereas, quenching sufficiently below T_m , produces a stress-bearing colloidal network. Gels were prepared by first dispersing a fixed volume fraction of fumed silica ϕ_{silica} in soybean oil (composed of liquid triglycerides such as trilinoleic). Mixtures were dispersed with a high-shear rotator operated at a maximum speed of 17500 rpm for $t = 5 \text{ min}$ ($\sim 8 \text{ m/s}$ tip speed for a 10 mm fixture)²⁰ to break up particle agglomerates into smaller aggregates which upon rest rapidly reaggregate to render a volume-spanning network. Molten tripalmitin ($75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) was then added to the preformed silica gel at increasing volume fractions $\phi_{\text{tripalmitin}}$, and held at $75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for $t = 5 \text{ min}$ to erase any

remaining ‘crystal memory’. Mixtures were then transferred and quenched to 5 °C to provide the driving force for melt-crystal phase transition. Aggregation was allowed to ensue at 21-22 °C for several days to ensure complete gelation. Approximate volume fractions for fumed silica ϕ_{silica} and tripalmitin $\phi_{\text{tripalmitin}}$ were obtained using densities of the materials. Total volume fraction of monogels and bigels are expressed as ϕ in all figures.

Likely sources of uncertainty in the estimation of volume fraction arise due to lower densities for high surface area silica nanoparticles, the ability of fumed silica aggregates to occlude a large amount of oil contributing to higher effective volume fraction, volume fraction of solid tripalmitin which is dependent on the density of the crystallizing polymorphic form, in addition to other systematic errors linked to the estimation of volume fractions in colloids.²¹

3D-printing of gels: Representative gels were printed at fixed total volume fraction $\phi = 0.10$ at room temperature using a 3D-bioplotter printer (envisionTEC) equipped with an extrusion nozzle of 440 μm . Prior to 3D printing, gels were prepared as earlier described and transferred to the printing syringe. For compression tests, single gels and bigels were printed into solid cylindrical shape specimens measuring 10 mm length by 10 mm diameter ($L/D = 1$).

Compression tests: Compression tests were conducted using a Zwick Roell testing system at a constant speed of 0.1 mm/s. Specimens were compressed a maximum of 0.8 mm. Force-displacement curves were converted to stress-strain curves considering area and initial height of the specimens. Elastic moduli were approximated as the slope of the lower portion of the strain-stress curve from the second loading cycle. The first loading cycle was applied to ensure specimens had nearly flat top surface prior to testing.

Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy: To allow visualization of the bigels, only fumed silica particles and the oil phase were labelled with Nile red at a final concentration of 80 $\mu\text{mol/L}$. A

Zeiss CLSM with a 63 \times oil-immersion objective (N.A.=1.4) is used to characterize the structure of the gels. Silica appear labeled as deep red (in single channel visualization) or yellow orange (in double channel visualization), whereas oil and tripalmitin appear labelled as green and black (i.e. negatively stained) respectively. Silica and oil were detected using two different excitation wavelengths: 488 nm and 633 nm, respectively. Intensity data were collected at emission wavelength ranges of 517-624 nm and 660-750 nm for each excitation wavelength, respectively. Images were collected at low $\phi_{\text{tripalmitin}}$ since higher densities gels preclude image acquisition due to multiple scattering and wall effects. 2D and 3D images stacks were acquired at a rate of 1 image/s, at heights $z \geq 10 \mu\text{m}$ away from the cover slip.

Rheology: Oscillatory shear viscoelastic moduli and yielding were investigated using frequency sweeps ($\omega = 0.1\text{-}100 \text{ rad/s}$) and strain sweeps ($\gamma_0 = 0.001\text{-}1000\%$, $\omega = 2 \text{ rad/s}$) respectively, in a rotational torque-controlled rheometer (MCR 301, Anton Paar). Thermal behavior was investigated by heating and cooling the Peltier units at the corresponding gelation rate. Samples were carefully loaded onto parallel-plate fixtures with radius $R = 10\text{-}60 \text{ mm}$ (smaller plate diameters were used for stiffer gel samples), which were previously covered with adhesive-back sandpaper (600 grit) to minimize wall slip. A gap height $h \approx 400\text{-}600 \mu\text{m}$ was used for all measurements after carefully transferring samples onto the rheometer plate. Varying gap and geometry diameter yielded comparably qualitative results and hence do not influence our findings. Elastic moduli were determined within the linear regime ($\gamma_0 = 0.01\%$), and ‘critical’ yield strains γ_c and yield stresses σ_c were determined at the onset of yielding (from the intersection between pre-yield and post-yield asymptotes in strain-stress curves) and ‘absolute’ yield strains γ_{abs} and yield stress σ_{abs} and stresses were determined at the cross-over point $G' = G''$ (from the intersection of cubic spline fits to G' and G'').²²

Results and discussion

Aggregation of the gels was achieved by sequential gelation by which the first silica gel network precedes the aggregation of the second tripalmitin gel network (Figure 1a). To this end, we mixed and equilibrated a three-component system at high temperature $T = 70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The ternary system contained a pre-existing silica network at fixed volume fraction: $\phi_{\text{silica}} = 0.01$, approximate to the minimum percolation concentration, dispersed in a triglyceride solution made of tripalmitin at increasing volume fraction $\phi_{\text{tripalmitin}} = 0.03\text{-}0.16$ and soybean oil. This leads to bigels with increasingly asymmetric mixture composition. Quenching was then performed by lowering the temperature to $20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at an approximate rate of $5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ well below the solid-liquid phase transition ($T_m \approx 48\text{-}58\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), to enable aggregation of tripalmitin gel within the pre-existing silica network. As gels are metastable amorphous solids, their structure is highly coupled to their thermal history. Aggregation ensued for several days to ensure complete gelation. To demonstrate the thermal responsiveness of the gels, we present a temperature sweep for a representative bigel, $\phi_{\text{silica}} = 0.01$, $\phi_{\text{bigel}} = 0.05$ (Figure 1b). During heating at $T \gtrsim 35\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the viscoelastic moduli G' and G'' drop as the tripalmitin crystal network, for both monogels and bigels, begins to melt and disintegrates at $T \gtrsim 55\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. At higher temperatures, elasticity is dominated by the silica network ($G'_{\text{bigel}}, T \gtrsim 55\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \sim G'_{\text{silica}}$ at $\phi_{\text{silica}} = 0.01$) only for bigels, whereas monogels become viscoelastic fluids. During the cooling interval, a thermal hysteresis appears since both monogels and bigel were allowed to fully crystallize and age over time and hence they exhibit higher elasticity G' (See Fig. S3, Supporting Information).

Figure 1. a) Schematic representation of a monogel (silica: sphere), and of a bigel of two interpenetrating particle networks (silica: sphere, tripalmitin: platelet), respectively. Colloidal particles are not monodisperse and are not drawn to scale. b) Macroscopic appearance of tripalmitin monogel and bigels are similar and are displayed before melting (right: opaque) and after melting (left: translucent). Silica monogels appear translucent throughout the temperature range. Viscoelastic moduli of monogels and bigels as a function of temperature. Particle concentrations are $\phi_{\text{silica}} = 0.01$ and $\phi_{\text{bigel}} = 0.05$ and $\phi_{\text{tripalmitin}} = 0.05$.

A key drive for understanding the structure and function of soft materials is to identify a suitable application that translates their properties from the nano-micro scales to the macroscale. Therefore,

we assessed the ability of the colloidal bigel inks to construct 3D structures using direct-ink writing.

Figure 2 demonstrates that the inks retain their shape when extruded through the nozzle and can be assembled into multiple self-supported patterned structures namely mesh, multi-walled cylinder and solid cylinders. This contrasts with polymeric materials where swelling can occur due to shear-induced alignment leading to printing defects. The printed structures displayed good resolution equivalent to the nozzle size ($\sim 400 \mu\text{m}$ line width), exhibited adequate structural consistency, that is multiple stacked layers where deposited without observing printing defects such as buckling or sagging. Solid cylinders of monogels and bigels were subjected to compression and their mechanics were compared at a fixed total ‘printable’ volume fraction $\phi = 0.10$ (Figure 2d). Comparing the loading strain-stress curves reveals that the maximum stress during compression σ_{max} of bigels falls in between that of the monogels. Estimation of the moduli yielded closer moduli for silica monogels and bigels: $E = 39.0 \pm 0.9$ and 38.7 ± 1.1 respectively, but not for tripalmitin monogels $E = 29.3 \pm 0.3$ kPa (see Figure S1, Supporting Information).

Figure 2. 3D printing of gels at total volume fraction $\phi = 0.10$. a) diameter of bigel at the exit of the printing nozzle corresponding to the inner nozzle diameter, scale bar= $440 \mu\text{m}$. b, c) examples

of 3D-printed shapes: filled solid cylinder (height= 10 mm) used for compression, multiwalled cylinder (height= 10 mm), and mesh illustrating the ‘printability’ of bigels. Similar printing characteristics were found for single gels provided that ϕ were matched. d) Loading and unloading curves of representative monogel and bigel cylinders at similar total volume fraction $\phi = 0.10$ of tripalmitin and silica.

Understanding the rheological properties of bigels has the potential to open up ways of controlling them, but up to this point, it remains an open question. Therefore, we investigated the shear rheology in a wide range of volume fractions that reflect increasingly asymmetric mixture compositions and characterize their microstructure to gain intuition on their unusual behavior (Figures 3 and 4). We place special emphasis on the mechanics of tripalmitin monogels and bigels, since ϕ_{silica} remains at a fixed packing fraction for all our experiments.

Figure 3. Shear rheological properties of monogels and bigel as a function of total volume fraction $\phi = \phi_{\text{silica}} + \phi_{\text{tripalmitin}}$. a) Linear plateau modulus G_0 , b) Adimensional relative modulus $G_r = G_0_{\text{bigel}} / G_0_{\text{experimental}}$ springs-in-parallel (See Equation 1), c) ‘absolute’ strain γ_{abs} and d) ‘absolute’ stress σ_{abs} at the crossover point from elastic-dominated to viscous-dominated behavior $G' = G''$. Dashed lines are power-law visual guides.

Frequency dependence of the viscoelastic moduli reveal that elastic contributions dominate viscous contributions $G' > G''$ in a broad range of timescales as expected for solid-like materials. Particle-concentration dependence (Figure 3a) of the linear modulus reveals that gels conform to power-law scaling $G'_0 \sim \phi^n$. This is expected since both colloidal silica and lipid particles have been reported to form self-similar scale-invariant structures at low densities.^{23,24} The values of the scaling of ~ 3.6 and ~ 5.5 for silica and tripalmitin monogels respectively are in good agreement with previous findings.^{24,25} In addition, bigels and tripalmitin monogels share similar exponents and exist in two regimes, indicating that the lipid network dominates the linear bulk response at same particle volume fraction. The similar scaling of the modulus, a measure of the dimensionality of fractal colloidal gels, suggests that average microscopic structural are absent. The simplest constitutive model to approximate the rigidity G_0 of multicomponent gels is by treating each specie as independent elastic elements or springs s connected in parallel:

$$G_0 \approx \sum_s c_s G_{0,s} \quad (1)$$

In this model, the total elastic constant is equivalent to the sum of linear elastic moduli $G_{0,s}$ times the mixture composition of each specie $c_s = \phi_s/\phi_{\text{total}}$, where ϕ_s corresponds to volume fraction of each ‘isolated’ specie s , and ϕ_{total} refers to the total volume fraction. Remarkably, we observe that such model underestimates the modulus by approximately up to an order of magnitude, but expectedly comes to close agreement at $\phi \gtrsim 0.1$ as $c_{\text{silica}} \rightarrow 0$. The observed stiffening at $\phi \lesssim 0.1$ suggests that ‘platelet-sphere’ cross contributions to the stress response could arise due to cooperative effects resultant from shear perturbations and irrespective of the non-interacting nature of the colloidal species. To elucidate this, we visualize the mesoscopic structure of tripalmitin monogels and bigels at similar volume fractions (Fig. 4 a-d) at ‘static’ conditions. At $\phi \lesssim 0.1$, the pre-existing silica network appears to promote more diffuse gel networks (that is large clusters

appear absent and particles appear more evenly distributed). Paradoxically, the finer texture of bigels should lead to lower elasticity than tripalmitin monogels as fewer bonds may form, however; interpenetration of bigel networks could account for the observed stiffening due to hindered particle rotation. Within this context, recent computational studies supports that gels made of highly-rough ‘less mobile’ colloids such as silica, display more locally-tenuous yet more rigid networks compared to smooth ‘more mobile’ colloids which favor more densely-packed but softer aggregates.²⁶ We speculate that a similar physical mechanism could occur in bigels by which, at more symmetric mixture compositions ($\phi \lesssim 0.1$), the silica network confers an energetic barrier that prevents cluster densification and promotes stiffening upon shear. At $\phi \gtrsim 0.1$, such effect reasonably vanishes as bigels become increasingly similar to pure tripalmitin monogels (See Figures S2 and S4, Supporting Information) and $c_{\text{silica}} \rightarrow 0$, consistent with rheological measures.

Figure 4. CLSM images of a, b, c) monogels and d) bigels at representative particle densities. Top and middle panels represent similar images at lower 2 \times and higher 3 \times magnifications. Oil, silica

and tripalmitin are assigned false colours: green, orange and black (negatively-stained) respectively to aid visualization.

Next, we draw comparisons on the nonlinear rheology of the gels as measured by the viscoelastic moduli, yield strain and stress at $\phi \lesssim 0.1$ (Figure 3). Expectedly, all gels strain-soften as the strain amplitude is increased beyond the linear regime, characteristic of colloidal gels (See Figure S3, Supporting Information). The critical strain to initiate yielding γ_c , but not the critical stress σ_c for bigels is lower than for tripalmitin monogels (See Supporting Information). Remarkably, to ‘fully’ yield $G' = G''$, bigels bear additional moderately larger deformations, $\gamma_{\text{abs}} \sim 20\%$ more, and much larger shear stresses, $\sigma_{\text{abs}} \sim 7$ times larger, compared to tripalmitin monogels (Figure 3 c, d). Similar qualitative behavior is observed at $\phi \gtrsim 0.1$ (See Figure S4, Supporting Information). This conveys an unexpected picture: on one side, bigels present a more-narrow linear regime, on the other, they ultimately bear larger deformations prior to fluidization $G' = G''$. The first behavior may be due to yielding initiating at the weakest link of the gel silica network in bigels. The second behavior suggests a self-healing mechanism that helps accommodating larger deformations.

Figure 5. Schematic illustration of suggested stiffening/yielding mechanism of a) bigels *versus* b) lipid monogels. Particles: spheres, silica and platelets, tripalmitin, red-contoured silica and platelet aggregates emphasize initial (left-side) and final position of particles/aggregates undergoing shear (right-side). Arrows indicate the direction of the applied shear. Restricted particle/aggregate mobility due to interpenetration of bigel networks leads to stiffening at small linear deformations, and delays fluidization ($G' = G''$) at large nonlinear deformations, compared to lipid monogels. c) Strain-stress curves of monogels and bigels at representative volume fractions. A two-step yielding emerges in bigels but not in monogels.

Recent numerical simulations in multicomponent gels, albeit made of identical spherical particles with short-range attraction and present at equal relative concentrations, can provide insight pertaining the mechanism for the unusual mechanical behavior of silica-tripalmitin bigels. While multicomponent gels formed thinner arms and displayed a reduced shear modulus, in contrast to our findings, these bigels also shared an ability to accommodate larger deformations as in the present study.² The proposed physical mechanism is that bigels undergo large non-affine displacements, originated from steric interactions between non-interacting species, that helps preserve the load-bearing structure for prolonged deformations and avoid network ‘breakage’ at similar strain inputs (Figure 5). Although we did not test for such spatial rearrangements during shear, it is possible that similar steric hindrance due to the non-interacting nature of silica and tripalmitin particles and non-affine shear underlie better preservation of the bigel structure.¹⁸ A possible manifestation of such mechanism is the emergence of a ‘two’ step yielding observed for bigels but not for monogels at $\phi \lesssim 0.1$.²⁷ An alternative microscopic picture for the strengthening of bigel networks is a decrease of the ‘localization length’ of the particles as suggested by theoretical predictions for mixed double gels arising from mixtures of ‘chemically-matched’ sticky

silica rods and attractive silica spheres.¹⁵ However, the nature of these effects is unclear, and difficult to quantify in the present systems.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, we have presented a new class of oil-continuous bigels made of interpenetrating networks from colloidal particles with short-range attraction: silica and lipid particles. Bigels are sequentially-assembled, thermo-responsive and present good resolution and structural consistency in 3D-printed constructs. Bigels can display much larger stiffness, up to an order of magnitude larger than that estimated by additive effects of the elastic constants or moduli ('springs-in-parallel'), and bear larger deformations (~20 % more) and stresses (~7 times larger) prior to switch from elastic to viscous dominated behavior, compared to their monogel counterparts. Despite of their seemingly more tenuous microstructure, bigels stiffening and toughening suggests cooperative effects between the non-mutually attractive gel networks that could be elicited during shear because of steric hindrance and restricted particle or aggregate mobility. A natural extension of our work is to explore broadly how bigel structure and mechanics varies with mixture composition to further extend the map of functionality of these materials. The approach presented here could be broadly generalized to the assembly of alkane-based colloids in apolar solvents and oils in which short-range attractive interactions can be thermally activated such as wax-based inks. This versatility makes bigels interesting candidates for a multitude of potential applications in consumer products and additive manufacturing of various soft materials.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information.

The following supporting information is available free of charge (PDF).

- Strain-stress curves from compression experiments of monogels and bigels
- Confocal microscopy of bigels at higher volume fractions.
- Temperature sweep, strain sweep at selected volume fractions, storage moduli, yield strain and stress as a function of volume fraction of monogels and bigels.

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Notes

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